

Effect of Career Development and Job Security on Employee Retention at the National Examination Council (NECO), Minna, Niger State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Employee retention globally has become a problem of concern to the management and employees of examination bodies. National Examination Council (NECO) employees are faced with the same problem and this is as a result of lack of career development and job security. This study examined the effect of career development and job security on employee retention at the National Examination Council Minna, Niger state, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted. The population was 1550 employees of NECO and the sample size was 647. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that that career development and job security has a significant positive effect on employee retention ($B = 1,226$; $R^2 = 0.662$, $P < 0.05$). The study concludes that career development and job security have significant effect on employee retention. The study recommended that the management of NECO should engage more in career development and job security to create an ambiance in the work environment that will encourage employee retention.

Keywords: Career development, Employee retention, Job security, Motivation, Job satisfaction

Word count: 149

Introduction

Employee retention in the educational sector has been a thing of concern around the world and Nigeria in particular. These concerns have become problematic as a result of the growing importance of education in shaping future leaders who will champion economic development and growth. Educational agencies depend on skills of competent workforce to thrive (Njanjobea, 2021). Employee retention is the organizational goal of keeping talented employees and reducing

turnover by fostering a positive work atmosphere to promote engagement, showing appreciation to employees, and providing career development, job security, competitive pay and healthy work-life balance (Lee, 2021). The strength of an organisation lies within the human resource department to ensure the efficiency of its practices in selection, training, employee motivation and retention of its employees (Mursalin & Aisyah, 2021). The challenges of career development in the Nigerian educational sector have led early and mid-career employees to begin to consider resigning as there are no clear career paths for them (Uche & Uche, 2024). Oftentimes due to these challenges, well-deserving employees are not given opportunities for training and development due to organizational politics, nepotism, greed and discrimination on the grounds of gender, race or ethnicity (Anekwe, Ndubuisi-Okolo 2028). Furthermore, it is observed that there is low productivity in educational institutions as a result of lack of proper mentoring and self-development (Gjedia & Gardinier, 2021).

Career development is the lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure and transitions in order to move towards a personally determined and evolving preferred future. According to Çigdem and Belgin (2024), administrators and school management need to understand that they cannot obtain good performance from staff in a platform where both personal career management and organizational career development practices are absent or conflicting. Osibanjo, Oyewunmi and Ojo (2024) added that career development is not a new issue, but the controversial aspect of it, is who should be responsible for its implementation. Umar, Shamsudin, Subramaniam and Johari (2023) discovered that the lack of proper career development in NECO leads to frustration and reduces productivity among staff, and therefore affects the tendency for their retention.

Job security is the assurance based on the structure and nature of the work that an individual will remain on his or her job for a longer period. Job security in NECO is crucial for staff in terms of keeping his or her job or finding a new one, and it is also important for the employers since it enables them to keep staff or find new ones (Saif & Adnan, 2019). Job security in NECO is an important factor in social life as well as in working life because it gives staff the assurance of being able to work for a long period and earning an income for the up keeping of their family. Observable in the Nigerian educational environment is that people settle for less when it comes to job conditions because they are afraid that it will be impossible or difficult to get another one (Evans,

2021). Shoss, Jiang and Probst (2021) indicated that the effect of job insecurity is not restricted to work settings alone but can also be detrimental to the behaviour of the staff out of work settings which might likely have an effect on the larger society.

According to studies (Reuben, 2019; Adedoyin, Exodus, Okere, & Okafor, 2021), Nigeria has roughly 36 branches of NECO offices nationwide. Despite the growing competition among these branches to gain acceptance and a competitive edge, several organisations in Nigeria are attempting to boost employee commitment in the current unstable and uncertain business climate (Ekeagbara, Ogunnaike, Ibidunni, & Kehinde, 2019). Many NECO personnel still exhibit negative behavioural outcomes such as low productivity, non-commitment, and low citizenship behaviour, according to Muchai, Makokha, and Namusonge (2021), which has impacted their performance toward the organisation's aims.

Uwannah, Eteete and Mark (2021) also claim that employee productivity is low as a result of poor employee retention at NECO. According to Odor, Martins-Emesom, and Bakwuye (2019), most employees of NECO in Nigeria are inefficient in their service delivery, as seen by the high number of candidates that fail examination on an annual basis. The effect of career development on employee productivity, job satisfaction, performance and motivation has been researched by various scholars (Kefelegn 2021). It was suggested from past literatures that further studies should fill the gap by conducting studies on career development and job security on employee retention in Nigeria.

In the Nigerian educational environment, Hassan, Baharom and Mutalib (2021) observed that employees are not given the required attention in terms of career development leading to job security and job retention. In most cases they are not sent for training as at when due, and when they are sent, the required financing for such trainings and conferences will not be adequate (Ojediran, 2021). Adenike (2022) discovered that employees are not given the required attention in terms of perceived organizational support. These issues therefore contribute to poor performance and productivity in terms of research, community service, teaching and eventual intention to leave the organization.

Similarly, job security is another area of concern for workers in the Nigerian educational sector. Employees carry out their jobs in the anticipation of the fact that there are risks, thereby implying that the feeling of job insecurity only occurs in the case of involuntary job loss. The feeling of job insecurity has been largely heightened among academic staff by its widespread observance among various organizations in Nigeria even in the educational sector. Universities sometimes due to the present economic situation and uncertainty in issues of profitability and survival have laid off workers (Joungtrakul, 2019). This therefore, created fear and uncertainty among those still employed.

In a nation where the unemployment rate is as high as 25%, job loss is a serious cause for psychological trauma among Nigerians. According to Aramide, Adebisi & Aderibigbe (2023), job insecurity reflects a fundamental and involuntary change concerning continuity and security within the employing organization. Therefore, it becomes a cause of worry for employees to either look for the exit door before they are thrown out or decide to accept low job conditions in order to secure their daily living. They become less committed to their jobs and their chances of being retained in the organization become very slim. This study therefore, based on the problems discussed above investigated the effect of career development and job security on employee retention at the National Examination Council, Minna Niger State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To what extent has career development and job security contributed to employee retention in NECO, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria.
2. To what extent has pay and promotional potentials contributed to employee retention in NECO, Minna, Niger State.

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Job Security

Job Security is the feeling employees enjoy working for the organisation without fear of adverse effects on self-image (Basharat, 2019; Tobias & Jochen, 2021). Individuals have a habit of feeling safe at work in a dependable workplace environment. Employees can be encouraged by ensuring

a work situation in which the intellect of employees supports the generation, promotion and realisation of inventive ideas in addition to concepts. It is expected that leaders and supervisors in the workplace will play an immense role in shaping job security. As an advantage, job security should inspire the standard of correspondence, prompting the commitment of employees to help the relationship achieve its goals, just as the desire to expand efforts to benefit the association would be seen and compensated.

In comparison, if people cannot trust other members of the organization, the workplace will be perceived as ambiguous, unpredictable and threatening (Sabbir 2021). On the other hand, once employees feel low association support, their immersion in enhancement will be conical. Trustworthiness therefore, largely influences the secure perception of the workplace environment (Basharat 2019). Besides the interaction history, cognitive trust is built on knowledge about the trustee. In the same way, employees who felt more experience of job security and enhanced needs-supplies suitable in addition to increased creativity.

According to Gharib, Kahwaji and Elrasheed (2021), job security can be viewed as the employment certainty from organizations that their employees will remain with them for a long period of time without being wrongly dismissed. Job security is defined as the assurance in an employee's job continuity due to the general economic conditions in the country (Maryatmi, 2020). It is the assurance from the organization that their employees will remain with them for a reasonable period of time without being wrongly dismissed (Lucky, Minai, & Rahman, 2023). It is concerned with the possibility or probability of an individual keeping his/her job (Adebayo & Lucky, 2022). It deals with the chances of employees keeping their jobs in order not be unemployed (Esuh, Mohd, & Hamzah, 2023). Jobs which are not backed by indefinite contract or cannot be guaranteed for reasonable periods are deemed to lack job security. It is also seen as the employees being free from the fear of being dismissed from his/her present employment or job loss. It is the assurance from the company or organization that their employees will remain with them for a reasonable period of time without being wrongly dismissed (Kraja, 2021).

Employee Retention

Employee retention refers to the various policies and practices which let the employees stick to an organization for a longer period of time (Haider, Rasli, Akhtar, Yusoff, Malik, Aamir, & Tariq, 2021). Employee retention is the ability to keep employees within an organization for the longer period of time. Talent retention is of critical importance for companies shifting from startup to fast growth. Keeping the best people closest to the organization's core competencies is important. The purpose of retaining employees is to avoid turnover cost. Organizations must retain the people who perform and have competencies and skills that match the business' core talent needs (Nasir & Mahmood, 2018).

Organizations with effective employee participation practices (direct and indirect) have more positive attitudinal outcomes (commitment, job and pay satisfaction, retention). When employees have effective role in devising policies and decisions within their organization, leaving the organization can become difficult for them (Ojasalo & Tahtinen, 2021). In developing countries like Nigeria, which offer limited financial compensation to their employees, employee participation practices could be an effective tool to retain employees (Hussain, Khan, & Hussain, 2020).

Employee retention refers to the techniques and procedures employed in the management of valuable employees to ensure that they do not leave their jobs (Johennesse & Chou, 2017). It details the steps taken to motivate and encourage employees to stay in the greatest possible working circumstances for as long as possible (Ambrosius, 2018). Because talent retention is critical, skilled and knowledgeable staff must be hired and managed properly.

This is critical since many businesses undervalue the expense of replacing personnel (Thiriku & Were, 2021). Benchmark inspections, temporary labour costs, training costs, and personnel entry charges are all examples of costs. Other unintended consequences include missing deadlines, a loss of organisational knowledge, lower morale, and bad customer perceptions of the organisation's image. For these reasons, many businesses place a high importance on retaining valuable employees. Employers who do not carefully manage employee retention, risk understaffing and

employee inefficiencies, which can have a direct impact on organisation's competitiveness, success, and long-term viability (Narayanan, Rajithakumar, & Menon, 2019).

Empirical Review

Job Security and Employee Retention

Researchers have shown that job security induces retention of workers. Davy, Kinicki and Scheck (2021) discovered that job security is significantly related to employee retention. Ashford, Lee and Bobko (2021) examined the impact of job insecurity on organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and job performance. Even though it is questionable whether job insecurity has an impact on job performance, it is certain that job insecurity has led to reduced commitment and reduced satisfaction. Abbeglen (2021) maintained that a high commitment level of Nigerian workers was due to a strong sense of job security, which originated from the unique Nigerian employment system, such as lifetime employment and the seniority system.

Mosaybian and Jafari (2022) examined the relationship between job security and organizational commitment. They employed correlation technique and it was observed that there is a significant relationship between job security and organizational commitment. They concluded that the success of any organization is due to its human resources and also satisfying related needs which are depended upon job security.

Imran, Majeed and Ayub (2023) studied the impact of organizational justice, job security and job satisfaction on organizational productivity. The study employed descriptive statistics and regression technique. The study found that employees' job security plays a very important role to enhance employee job commitment to the organization and in the end, organizational productivity will be increased. They asserted that job security, job satisfaction and organizational justice, the productivity of any organization can be increased.

Similarly, Jimenez and Didona (2022) investigated the perceived job security and its effects on job performance. They employed quantitative research method and correlation technique. The study found that there is a significant positive correlation between the perception of job security and job performance and this means that the more secure an employee feels at a job, the better he or she

will perform. They asserted that strong benefits package, probability of advancement, employee participation in the provision and status of the employment, and opportunity for personal growth and development may all play a significant role in the employees' perception of job security, and turn, have an impact on employee commitment.

Theoretical Framework

Job Embeddedness Theory

Job embeddedness was first introduced by Mitchell, Holtom, Lee, Sablinski, Erez (2021) in an effort to improve traditional employee turnover models. According to these models, factors such as job satisfaction and organizational commitment and the individual's perception of job alternatives together predict an employee's intent to leave and subsequently, turnover. Job embeddedness is the collection of forces that influence employee retention (Shibiti, 2019). It can be distinguished from turnover in that its emphasis is on all of the factors that keep an employee on the job, rather than the psychological process one goes through when quitting (Akgunduz & Sanli, 2021).

The scholars who introduced job embeddedness described the concept as consisting of three key components (links, fit, and sacrifice), each of which are important both on and off the job. Job embeddedness is therefore conceptualized as six dimensions: links, fit, and sacrifice between the employee and organization, and links, fit and sacrifice between the employee and the community (Yam, Raybould, & Gordon, 2021).

According to Mitchell and Lee (2021), job embeddedness theories that employee will stay in an organisation as long as the incentives to stay match or exceed their expectations. Employees' decisions to stay or go are influenced by their job embeddedness. Individuals who are immersed in their jobs are less inclined to leave the company, which has a beneficial impact on their performance.

Employees establish a network of connectedness and interactions on and off the job as they participate in their professional and communal lives (Coetzer, Inma, Poisat, Redmond, & Standing, 2018). Organizations should guarantee that their employees are job embedded because this will prevent them from leaving, resulting in employee retention. Through the three characteristics of

employment embeddedness: linkages, fit, and sacrifice, human resource practitioners should aim to guarantee that people are embedded in their jobs (Holtom & Darabi, 2021).

The links dimension describes the employee's interactions with other members of the organisation. Educational institutions can manage links by assigning mentors to staff, allowing students to work in groups, and encouraging teamwork. Coworkers, work groups, mentors, friends, relatives, and so on are examples. Employees that have many connections inside their institution and community are more embedded and would find it more difficult to quit (Ferreira, 2017). Employees will be more committed to their jobs if they have good relationships at work, which may be achieved by having them work in teams.

The second dimension of fit refers to an employee's compatibility with their work and in the workplace. When an employee decides to quit an organisation, he or she will experience and bear sacrifice. When an employee leaves the company, he or she will forfeit fascinating initiatives, appealing benefits and compensation, the opportunity to work with colleagues with whom they have grown close, and promotion opportunities. As a result, job embeddedness is advantageous to organisations when it comes to maintaining employees because it allows them to understand why people choose to stay, allowing them to develop retention tactics that are tailored to their needs (Lyu & Zhu, 2019).

Methodology

The study focused on the effect of career development and job security on employee retention in NECO Minna Niger state, Nigeria. The study adopted a quantitative methodology, the design was survey research design. A total of 647 sample size was given from the population of 1550 employees of NECO through the use of Taro Yamane formula. The study adopted the simple random sampling technique in sampling the respondents from the selected units. An adapted and validated questionnaire was used to gather primary data from the respondents. Cronbach's Alpha and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test were used to test the validity and reliability of the data from the pilot study. Descriptive analysis and inferential analysis using simple regression analysis and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation test were used to test the hypothesis

Results & Discussions

Regression analysis

Table 1: Summary of Regression Result for the Effect of Career Development and Job Security on Employee Retention in NECO, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	9.004	1.081		8.329	.000
Job Security	1.226	.036	.814	33.779	.000
R = 0.814, R2 = 0.662, P< 0.05 alpha					

Dependent Variable: Employee Retention

Interpretation

The results in the table above shows that job security has significant effect on employee retention in NECO Minna, Niger State, Nigeria ($\beta = 1.226$, $t = 33.779$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that job security significantly predicted employee retention in NECO Minna, Niger State Nigeria. The results also shows that career development explained about 66.2% of the variance in employee retention in NECO ($R^2 = 0.662$, $p < 0.05$). The findings imply that Career Development is a determinant of employee retention in National Examination Council (NECO) Minna, Niger State Nigeria. The equation found for the regression was the following:

$$ER = 9.004 + 1.226 CD$$

Where:

ER = Employee Retention,

CD = Career Development

The regression equation illustrated in the table has established that taking career development and all factors into account all other factors held constant employee retention increased 9.004. Findings also showed that with all other variables held at zero, a unit increase in career development yielded a 1.226 change in Employee Retention in selected private universities in NECO. Which implies that an increase in career development will subsequently increase employee retention in NECO Minna, Niger State Nigeria.

Thus, the null hypothesis which states that Career development does not significantly affect employee retention in NECO is not accepted.

Discussion

The findings of this hypothesis confirm that career development significantly affects employee retention in NECO. The work of Tangthong and Agahi (2018) empirically established that employee development is the most crucial Human Resource Management function in the organization and it refers to developing employees and organization's abilities as a whole. In support of this findings, Khadijetou (2022) found that career development programmes affect employee retention. Also, he established that organizational Career planning is an important fundamental human resource policy. Adeoye and Egwake(2019) found out that career development had effect on talent retention in NECO. Pillay, Dawood and Karodia (2021), discovered that career development has a highly positive correlation on employee motivation and intention to stay with an organization. Similarly, Kefelegn (2023) examined the effect of career development on staff motivation and retention. Descriptive and explanatory analysis was used. Furthermore Wane (2023), confirmed that career development programmes significantly affects employee retention.

Nivern, Quraisha and Anis (2021), established that career development has a significant relationship with staff motivation. Osibanjo, Oyewunmi, Ojo (2024), confirmed that career development practices such as reward, recognition, skills, promotion had positive impact on organizational growth. Soares and Mosquera (2021) in their study concluded that career management practices such as mentoring, job posting, career planning, and performance review have a significant impact on employee engagement. Shujaat, Aftab, Sana and Ahmed (2023) agreed that there is a positive relationship between career development and job satisfaction, which

leads to increased employee retention. However, Kaya and Ceylan (2024) on the other hand, found in their study that career development programmes in organizations do not affect the level of employee’s job satisfaction and retention. Omerzel and Gulev (2021) empirically deduced that organizations need to adopt the development of employees so as to foster a sound organizational memory. This will in turn enable employees to develop capabilities needed to remember what had previously worked as well as what previously failed. This will enhance sound and prompt execution of tasks as organizational information can be retrieved to enhance better employee performance.

Correlation analysis

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation between Career Development and Job security on Employee Retention in NECO

		Job	Security
Employee Retention			
Job Security	Pearson Correlation	1	.628
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	584	584
Employee Retention	Pearson Correlation	.628	1
	Sig (2-Tailed)		.000
	N	584	584
584			

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation

Table 2 presents results of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient on the relationship between career development and job security on employee retention in National Examination Council, Minna Niger State Nigeria. The result shows that the correlation between career development and job security on employee retention is strong, positive and significant ($r = 0.628$, $p < 0.05$). The significance value for relationship between career development and job security on employee retention was 0.000. Which implies that there is a significant relationship between career development and job security on employee retention in NECO. This also, implies that an increase in career development and job security will lead to an increase in employee retention in NECO. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between career development and job security on employee retention of staff of NECO Minna Niger State is hereby rejected.

Discussion

The analysis of this hypothesis revealed that a significant relationship exists between career development and job security on employee retention in NECO. This finding is in agreement with other empirical findings in literature. Davy, Kinicki and Scheck (2022) discovered that career development and job security are significantly related to employee retention. Abbeglen (2021) maintained that a high commitment level of Nigeria Civil Service workers was due to a strong sense of job security, which originated from the unique Nigerian employment system, such as lifetime employment and the seniority system. Mosaybian and Jafari (2022) examined the relationship between career development and job security on organizational commitment. They employed correlation technique and it was observed that there is a significant relationship between job security and organizational commitment. They concluded that the success of any organization is due to its human resources and also satisfying related needs which are depended upon job security.

Imran, Majeed and Ayub (2023) studied the impact of organizational justice, job security and job satisfaction on organizational productivity. The study found that employees' job security plays a very important role to enhance employee job commitment to the organization and in the end,

organizational productivity will be increased. Ashford, Lee and Bobko (2021) showed that even though it is questionable whether job insecurity has an impact on job performance, it is certain that job insecurity has led to reduced commitment, reduced satisfaction and retention. Ismail (2021) ascertained that there is a significant positive impact of job insecurity on intention to quit. Which implies that job security has a significant positive impact on employees' decision to remain in an organization, that is, employee retention. This finding was in agreement with the research by Khan, Nawaz, Aleem and Hamed (2022), in their study also discovered that job safety/ security significantly related to retention and performance. Abdullah and Ramay (2022), reported a significant positive relationship between job security and organizational retention of employees. This certifies that job security induces employee retention in any work situation.

In other words, employees who perceive threat of job security may become less committed to the organization they are working for and may decide to quit the job. Similarly, Imenez and Didona (2022) investigated the perceived job security and its effects on job performance. They employed quantitative research method and correlation technique. The study found that there is a significant positive correlation between the perception of job security and job performance and this means that the more secure an employee feels at a job, the better he or she will perform.

They asserted that strong benefits package, probability of advancement, employee participation in the provision and status of the employment, and opportunity for personal growth and development may all play a significant role in the employees' perception of job security, and turn, have an impact on employee commitment. Davy, Kinicki and Scheck (2023), discovered in their research that career development and job security are significantly related to employee retention. This view was also supported by Akpan (2023), who revealed that both job security and job satisfaction jointly had a significant effect on organizational commitment and consequently on employee retention.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that career development and job security have significant effect on employee retention. The study recommends that National Examination Council should ensure that career development practices policies are properly enforced so as to create an ambience in the work environment. Also employee job security should be adequately provided for their employees. This

will provide sense of self belonging and commitment to their employers which will lead to employee retention. This study was limited to National Examination Council Minna, Niger State, this has provided opportunities for future researchers, hence limitation of generalizability of results. Further studies can be carried out in other sectors to examine how career development and job security affects employee retention.

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